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Azine and Oxazine Dyes as Redox Indicators in Cerate Oxidimetry*

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DURING recent times, some azine and oxazine dyes have been reported as redox indicators in cerate oxidimetry¹⁻⁶. The present communication describes the results of our investigations on the use of an azine dye, Lissamine Blue BF (LBBF), and four oxazine dyes, Sevron Blue 5G (SB5G), Brilliant Cresyl Blue (BCB), Alizarin Blue S (ABS), and Resorcin Blue (RB) (Colour Index Nos. 50230, 51004, 51010, 51080 and 51400 respectively) as redox indicators in the titration of iron(II), arsenic(III), antimony(III), uranium(IV), vanadium(IV), molybdenum(V), hydroquinone and oxalic acid with ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) in perchloric acid medium. The advantages of these indicators are: relative cheapness, solubility in water and stability of the aqueous solutions.

Experimental

0.1 *N* solution of arsenic(III) was prepared from E. Merck 'pro analysi' grade arsenious oxide. 0.1 *N* solutions of iron(II), antimony(III), uranium(IV), vanadium(IV) (oxovanadium(IV)), molybdenum(V) (oxomolybdenum(V)), hydroquinone, oxalic acid and ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) (in 1.0 *M* perchloric acid) were prepared and standardised.

0.1% solutions of the dyes were prepared in deionised water from the following samples of dyes, without any further purification:—LBBF: Gurr; BCB: E. Merck; SB5G: du Pont; ABS and RB: Chroma. The dye solutions retained their indicator action for about six months.

General Procedure. Treat an aliquot of the reductant solution with enough 1:1 perchloric acid (70%), dilute to 50 ml and titrate with 0.1 *N* ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) solution employing the prescribed quantity of any one of the following indicators:—LBBF and BCB: 0.1 ml; SB5G and ABS: 0.15 ml; RB: 0.5 ml.

The conditions of titrations are given in Table 1 and the colour changes at the end points are:—LBBF: violet to pink (light pink to light yellow with V(IV)); SB5G: green (blue with arsenic(III)) to pink; BCB: green to pink; ABS: violet to colourless with Fe(II), pink to colourless with As(III) and oxalic acid and pale pink to pale yellow with hydroquinone; RB: pale pink to colourless.

The results obtained with all these indicators are in excellent agreement with those obtained by other standard methods; for example, the mean experimental errors for the different reductants, using LBBF as indicator, are as follows:—Fe(II): 0.16%; As(III): 0.10%; Sb(III): 0.09%; U(IV): 0.14%; V(IV): 0.15%; Mo(V): 0.05%; hydroquinone: 0.11%; oxalic acid: 0.06%.

LBBF, SB5G and BCB (but not ABS and RB) function satisfactorily in titrations involving 0.01 *N* solutions of the reductants with 0.01 *N* solutions of ammonium hexanitratocerate(IV) also.

Indicator Corrections. An indicator correction of 0.04 ml is required while titrating with 0.01 *N* solutions of the oxidant whereas titrations involving 0.1 *N* solutions do not require any indicator correction.

Reverse Titrations. LBBF and BCB are the only suitable indicators in the reverse titrations, i.e., titrations of the cerate(IV) with the reductants, iron(II), molybdenum(V), and hydroquinone, under the same conditions of direct titrations. SB5G, ABS and RB are not suitable in titrations of these as well as other reductant systems.

Transition Potentials. The transition potentials, *mV* vs N.H.E., of the indicators in the iron(II)–cerate(IV) titration are:—LBBF: 950 ± 15; SB5G: 1185 ± 10; ABS: 825 ± 10; RB: 915 ± 15; BCB: 980 – 1040 (value reported by Sriramam⁴).

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TABLE 1—CONDITIONS OF TITRATIONS

Indicator	Reductant (s)	Acidity range, M
LBBF	Fe(II), Sb(III) and hydroquinone	1.0–3.0
	As(III) ^α	1.0–2.0
	U(IV), Mo(V) and oxalic acid	0.5–1.5
	V(IV)	0.2–0.4+6.0–8.0 M acetic acid.
SBSG	Fe(II) and hydroquinone	1.0–2.0
	Sb(III), As(III) ^α and Mo(V)	1.5–3.0
	Oxalic acid	0.5–1.5
	U(IV) and V(IV)	Titration is not satisfactory
BCB ^β	Sb(III), As(III) ^α and hydroquinone	1.0–2.0
	U(IV) and oxalic acid	0.5–1.5
	Mo(V)	2.0–4.0
	V(IV)	0.2–0.4+6.0–8.0 M acetic acid.
ABS ^φ	Fe(II) and hydroquinone	1.0–2.0
	As(III) ^α	1.5–3.0
	Oxalic acid	0.5–1.5
	Sb(III), U(IV), V(IV) and Mo(V)	Titration is not possible.
RB ^φ	Fe(II)	1.0–2.0
	Sb(III)	1.5–3.0
	Oxalic acid	0.5–1.5
	As(III) ^α , U(IV), V(IV), Mo(V), and hydroquinone	Titration is not possible.

^α 5–8 drops of 0.25% osmic acid or 0.5 ml of 0.005 M ferron is used as catalyst.

^β Sriramam^{*} has reported BCB as indicator in the Fe(II)-cerate (IV) titration.

^φ The indicator should be added at about 0.5–1.0 ml before the end point.

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A Semiempirical Relation for the Interaction Moment

$\Delta\mu$ in H-Bonded Complexes

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IN H-bonding, in addition to major electrostatic interaction, delocalization, dispersion and repulsive interactions also play an appreciable role¹. However the

stronger H-bonds with large interaction moment $\Delta\mu$ along the A-H...B axis ($\mu_{\text{complex}} - \mu_{\text{AH}} - \mu_{\text{B}}$) in the cases of complexes of picric and hydrobromic acid with trialkylamines can be explained only on the basis of proton transfer effect²⁻⁴. Ratajczak et al.,^{5,6} made

an attempt to understand the influence of $\Delta\mu$ on the strength and polarity of hydrogen bonds by considering both inductive and tautomeric effects and showed that the polarity of H-bonds mainly depends on the acidity of A-H, the p_K value of the acidic component. They also found that the enhancement of dipole moment in triethylamine-phenols complex³ in nonpolar solvents changes continuously within a wide range from 0.30 to

about 10.00 D. To account such high polarity ($\Delta\mu > 3.0$ D) they suggested the possibility of proton transfer complexes with an equilibrium of type

and the interaction moments in the range 3–10 D may be due to the coexistence of H-bonded and proton transfer complexes. The existing proton transfer equilibrium leads to the linear relationship between $\Delta\mu$ and

the mole fraction of proton transfer species. i.e., $\Delta\mu = A + Bx$, where A is the dipole moment of non-proton transfer complexes and B, the dipole moment of ion-

pairs. $\Delta\mu$, in complexes with a fixed electron donating and α varying electron accepting groups, in general, rises with an increase in acidity of A-H (fall in p_K)